

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

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An Appraisal of Intercultural Competence as a Predictor of Effective Pastoral Counselling

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Abstract

One vital quality which a pastoral counsellor should possess is intercultural competence. Intercultural competence refers to the ability to understand, appreciate, and adapt to different cultural norms, values, and communication styles. This paper looks into the place of intercultural competence in effective pastoral counseling. Intercultural competence is very vital because the counselling profession is relational and because all counselling is cross-cultural—the counsellor deals with clients who are culturally varied in terms of race, ethnicity, social economic status, educational background, family background, age and gender. This means that pastoral counselling cannot be done the same way with every client. The ability of the counsellor to cross to the culture of the client, while still retaining his own culture, requires intercultural competence. The author adopted the Fantini's model to describe the four dimensions in which intercultural competence can be measured. They are: intercultural knowledge, intercultural attitude, intercultural skill and intercultural awareness. Intercultural competence enables effective intercultural communication, which in turn results in effective pastoral counselling. This work reveals that this competence can be developed through conscious efforts. An interculturally competent counsellor is more likely to address the client's major problems more effectively due to the counsellor's ability to approach counselling within the context of the client's world. It is recommended in this paper that pastoral counsellors should undergo periodic assessment tests on intercultural competence so that areas of needed adjustment could be identified and proper adjustments made.

Keywords: Intercultural Competence, Pastoral Counsellor, Counselling, Effective, Culture

Introduction

Many scholars in the field of Counselling have highlighted the essential qualities which a pastoral counsellor needs to possess. For instance, Adams mentions spiritual knowledge of

the will of God, divine wisdom in one's relationship to others and good will and concern for other members of the body of Christ as requisite qualities of a good pastoral counsellor (Adams, 1986). Collins lists seven qualities of effective counselors which are: psychological health, a genuine interest in people, empathy, personal warmth, self-awareness, awareness of values and tolerance of ambiguity (Collins, 2007). In the opinion of Odeleye, a pastoral counselor should possess the following characteristics: adept knowledge of the Bible, a lifestyle of prayer and meditation, pragmatic preaching and teaching skill, maintaining confidentiality, empathy, new birth experience, a personal life of purity, fruit of the spirit, attentive listening and referral (Odeleye, 2022). Yet, there is a vital quality which a pastoral counselor should possess and which has not been so much emphasized—that is intercultural competence. Thus, the focus of this paper is to look into the place of intercultural competence in doing an effective pastoral counseling. For the purpose of this study, "culture" encompasses ethnicity, race, gender, social and economic status, educational background and the like and "pastoral counsellor" refers to a Christian or biblical counsellor.

Effective Pastoral Counselling

According to Sohn (1951), pastoral counseling is such "a personal and dynamic relationship between two or more people, one of whom is a pastor, who approach a problem for the purpose of finding a solution to it on the proper basis." It should be noted from the above definition that counselling work is relationship between two or more people who may be coming from different cultural orientations. Collins defines pastoral counselling as a "more specialized part of pastoral care that involves helping individuals, families, or groups as they cope with the pressures and crises of life (Adams, 1986)." These "individuals" usually are culturally varied in terms of race, ethnicity, social economic status, educational background, family background, age, etc. Odeleye submits that "pastoral counselling is a therapeutic relationship between a congruent, stable and coordinated pastoral counsellor and an incongruent, disturbed and confused counsellee (church member, congregant)." He, however, notes that there are times when the counsellee is not exactly disturbed or confused but will just like to seek more information or clarification on certain issues of interest (Odeleye, 2022). One common denominator in all these definitions is that counselling is essentially relational and because the counsellor and his client are often culturally varied, the counsellor will be crossing from his own culture to the culture of the counsellee. This suggests that, in addition to other qualities earlier mentioned, the pastoral counsellor must be interculturally competent in order to have an effective pastoral counselling.

Intercultural Competence

Intercultural competence is generally understood to be someone's ability to interact appropriately and effectively with others in possession of different cognitive, affective, and behavioural orientations towards the world in intercultural situations (Hang & Zhang, 2023). According to Zelenková and Hanesová, an interculturally competent person can be described as a person "not only with some acquired knowledge on culture and its cognitive comprehension, but also competent to demonstrate intercultural empathy, respect, tolerance,

sensitivity and flexibility, as well as the openness to negotiate, the ability to argue, the good will to understand others, discuss with them, and reach consensus (Zelenková & Hanesová, 2019)."

Thus, interculturality penetrates into all three dimensions of personality and relationships. For instance, it penetrates into the cognitive domain because a person should be aware of his own culture and other people's cultures before he could be deemed to be interculturally competent. It also penetrates into the affective domain because such a person is expected to be empathetic, tolerant and appreciative of cultural diversities. Lastly, intercultural competence penetrates into the behavioural domain because such a person is expected to possess good interaction and cooperation skills. Therefore, intercultural competence refers to the ability to understand, appreciate, and adapt to different cultural norms, values, and communication styles.

The concept of intercultural competence was first muted by Bennett, who proposed a developmental approach to training for intercultural sensitivity. He suggests that individuals with intercultural sensitivity tend to transform themselves from the ethnocentric stage to the ethno-relative stage. By ethnocentrism he refers to the experience of looking at one's own culture as central to reality. Beliefs, values and behaviours acquired through primary socialization are seen as adequate descriptors of the way things are. By ethnorelativism he refers to the experience of viewing one's own culture as just one organization of reality amongst many legitimate possibilities. This developmental model is a conceptual framework that describes the stages individuals go through as they develop intercultural competence. Bennett identifies six distinct types of experience across the continuum from ethnocentrism to ethno-relativism: denial, defense, minimization, acceptance, adaptation and integration. Each stage represents a different level of intercultural sensitivity and competence. These stages provide a good framework for determining how to improve the capacity for intercultural competence (Bennett, 1986).

Another influential scholar is Michael Byram. Byram makes a significant contribution to the field of intercultural competence in the context of language education. He emphasizes the importance of developing intercultural communicative competence, stressing that this competence goes beyond language proficiency to include one's ability to appreciate and navigate cultural diversity (Byram, 2020).

Several other scholars have subsequently contributed by applying the concept of intercultural competence to several areas of human endeavour: from education, business, economy and politics to religion and military work. For instance, Han calls for adult education and Human Resource Development professionals to acquire intercultural competence by applying adult learning theories in cross-cultural learning, in order to help various people from diverse cultural backgrounds. He believes this will help them to become successful in their international assignments (Han, 2010). Hang and Zhang are of the opinion that the rate of worldwide mobility of students and increasing globalization and internationalization of university and college campuses call for the cultivation of students' intercultural competence. They believe that this will enable them to communicate effectively on campus and even in campuses outside their home countries (Hang & Zhang, 2023).

Olagbaju discusses how education, with Literature-in-English as a tool, can be used to teach intercultural communicative competence in multicultural classrooms in Nigeria, thereby facilitating cross-cultural competence. He identifies cultural diversity as one of the major factors responsible for incessant civil unrest, hate speeches and insecurity in different parts of the country (Olagbaju, 2020).

Bradford and Bradford apply the concept to the U.S Navy. They stress that the Sea Services must reinforce their relationship with global maritime partners and in order for this to be possible the force has to embrace international organizations, local mariners and commercial operators. The diversity of partners and their cultural backgrounds would necessitate the mariners' intercultural competence to be built over time (Bradford & Bradford, 2008). Tucker and others look at intercultural competence with respect to its importance in global leadership. According to them, for business organizations to be successful, they need leaders who can drive business on a global scale. In these days of globalization and high competitiveness, no major company can be satisfied with being successful in the home market, or even in one or two cross-border markets. Even if a major company chooses not to expand globally, international competitors will enter its favorite markets. These scholars therefore submit that leading across cultures is a critical element in driving a business enterprise to a great success (Tucker, Bonial, Vanhove & Kedhamath, 2014).

Cross-cultural Nature of Counselling

According to Collins, "all counselling is cross-cultural." He believes that cross-cultural issue in counselling does not have to do with tribal, racial or ethnic affiliations alone. "You are counselling cross-culturally if you work with someone of an age, background, gender, level of education, set of values, socio-economic status, belief system and sexual orientation that differs from yours (Collins, 2007)." Of course, all of the above elements combine to form an individual's worldview. This implies that pastoral counselling cannot be applied the same way to every client. The counsellor should be able to cross to the culture of the counsellee. This may account for why the biblical Paul says:

And unto the Jews I became as a Jew, that I might gain the Jews; to them that are under the law, as under the law, that I might gain them that are under the law; To them that are without law, as without law, (being not without law to God, but under the law to Christ,) that I might gain them that are without law. To the weak became I as weak, that I might gain the weak: I am made all things to all men, that I might by all means save some (1Corinthians 9.20-22).

During His earthly ministry, Jesus was always aware of cultural differences. His counselling, preaching and one-on-one contacts revealed His awareness of cultural differences. The way He talked with the Samaritan woman was quite different from the way He approached Jewish leaders, fishermen, or Roman officers like Pilate or Herod (Collins, 2007).

Augsburger, one of the pioneers of cross-cultural pastoral counselling, once argued for the need for a culturally capable (or competent) pastoral counsellor who possesses the ability to join another in their culture while fully retaining his own culture. His objective was to assist in training culturally able counsellors who will be able to cross over effectively into another culture while still retaining their own (Augsburger, 1986). This means that for pastoral

counsellors to be effective, they should be able to cross over to the culture of the client, without losing their own cultural values.

Dimensions of Intercultural Competence (Fantini's Model)

One popular categorization of intercultural competence is the one given by Fantini in his assessment scale. He divides intercultural competence into four dimensions which are: intercultural knowledge, intercultural attitude, intercultural skill and intercultural awareness. These four dimensions can be used for self assessment.

Intercultural Knowledge: This dimension is also considered as the conceptual aspect of intercultural competence. Intercultural knowledge is taken into consideration as an individual's skills to have relevant information which would help the individual to interact with people from the other culture personally. This includes knowledge of the essential norms and taboos of the host culture; knowledge of the history of the host community; ability to cite important historical and socio-political factors that shape one's culture and the host culture and the ability to contrast important aspects of the host language and culture with one's own in a cross-cultural setting.

Intercultural Attitude: This dimension includes being curious about different cultures, being empathic, open-minded and having respect for differences. Therefore, the following are some of the variables under intercultural attitude: ability to interact with people of other cultures, learn from them, eat local foods, feel safe and use the native dress in a cross-cultural setting. It also includes showing interest in new cultural aspects and dealing with emotions and frustrations with other cultures.

Intercultural Skill: The ability to listen to people from other cultures, observe other cultures, interpret, analyse, evaluate and relate them. Besides, skills to learn a second or third language, skills to stand up to the difficulties faced during the process of learning a second or third language, skills to interrelate languages with each other, listening skills, information gathering skills and problem-solving skills are among the intercultural skills.

Intercultural Awareness: This refers to individual's ability to see the similarities and differences between their own culture and the other culture with a criticising point of view. The following are some of the variables under intercultural awareness: being aware of differences and similarities across one's own culture and another culture; being aware of diversity in the host culture and being aware of one's personal values affecting one's approach to ethical dilemmas in a cross-cultural setting (Fantini, 2007).

Therefore, a person can be said to be interculturally competent having possessed the skills mentioned above.

Impact of Intercultural Competence on Pastoral Counselling

Intercultural competence enables effective intercultural communication, which in turn results in effective pastoral counselling. Intercultural competence involves much more than mastering a foreign language or understanding non-verbal communication. Gleaning from the opinion of scholars above, it is the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately with others having different cultural backgrounds, and because counselling is communication

and cross-cultural, lack of intercultural competence leads to misunderstanding and the breaking of relationships. Cultural stereotypes have been found to be among the most important barriers to effective intercultural communication. Intercultural competence eliminates communication obstacles such as misunderstandings because of cultural differences, cultural stereotypes, and language barriers (Szóke, 2018).

Pastoral Counsellor's Intercultural Competence Development

The American Psychological Association has published a list of terms for counselling ethics when engaging with clients of linguistic and culturally diverse populations. The list includes:

- Counsellors should educate their clients on the goals, expectations and scope of counseling as well as the counselor's own orientation.
- Counsellors should acknowledge ethnicity and culture as important parameters in understanding psychological processes.
- Counsellors should respect the roles of family and community values and beliefs in the client's culture.
- Counsellors should try to communicate in the language requested by the client. If this is not possible, the client can be referred to another counsellor.
- Counsellors should try to eliminate biases and prejudices (Khoo, Abu-Rasain & Hornby, 2002).

Collins' opinion goes in line with the foregoing. He provides five multicultural competencies which a Christian counsellor needs to learn and practice:

- The counsellor should develop awareness of his/her own cultural values and biases.
- This could happen through personal assessment of one's biases which could negatively affect the counselling process. External assistance could be sought for a proper assessment to be done.
- The counsellor should try and become aware of the cultural background of each counsellee. This implies a deliberate search for facts about the different groups the counsellor encounters.
- The counsellor should seek to understand the ways in which culturally diverse counsellees see the world.

This could be made possible through a deliberate effort to make friends or relate with people who are culturally different.

- The counsellor could benefit from an understanding of cultural adaptation.
- This means that he should be ready to walk through the acculturation process.
- The counsellor should develop and use appropriate counselling strategies and techniques (Collins, 2007). For instance, counsellors should respect their client's religious views, values, beliefs, indigenous practices, and languages.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It has been established through this paper that pastoral counsellors have an obligation to grow in intercultural competence in order to be effective. The counselling relationship becomes strengthened when a counsellor is interculturally competent. An interculturally competent

counsellor is more likely to address the client's major problems more effectively due to the counsellor's ability to approach counselling within the context of the client's world. Therefore, counsellor's own cultural values or bias must not take precedence over that of the client. It is recommended that pastoral counsellors undergo periodic assessment tests on intercultural competence so that areas of needed adjustment could be identified and proper adjustments made. The counsellor can make use of Fantini's dimensions of intercultural competence mentioned above for self-assessment (Fantini, 2007).

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